

POLITICAL SCIENCES

THE TENDENCIES OF DEMOCRATIC REFORMS IN THE EUROPEAN UNION AND SOUTH CAUCASIAN COUNTRIES

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Abstract

The article looks at the modern-day relations between the European Union (EU) and the South Caucasus countries as well as, the trends of democratic reforms in the three countries respectively (Georgia, Azerbaijan, Armenia). The EU, as one of the most successful integration unions in the world, has rather multifaceted relations with the South Caucasian countries. The challenges in these relations were posed by the differing foreign policy orientations of all three countries.

Over the years, the EU has been implementing a policy of close cooperation with the South Caucasian states within the framework of its "Neighbourhood Policy" through supporting democratic reforms and strong state institutions. In consideration of the modern international geopolitical realities, the EU made no attempts to transform the political regimes in the countries of the South Caucasus, but rather focused on mutually beneficial relations. This especially applies to relations with Armenia and Azerbaijan. As for Georgia, it has to strictly fulfil many stipulations on its way to democratic reforms.

Keywords: The European Union, South Caucasus, Georgia, Azerbaijan, Armenia, Democracy, Reforms.

Introduction

At present, the EU's relations with South Caucasian states are becoming particularly relevant with the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022 serving as a final breaking point in convincing the EU in Russia's unreliability as a partner. Since the EU has been considerably decreasing its energy dependence on Russia this created a need to find alternate means.

It is common knowledge that Azerbaijan is rich with energy resources, in addition, the South Caucasus is a strategically important corridor enabling the EU to engage in broad trade and economic relations with Central Asia and China. Moreover, the EU maintains multilateral relations with all three states (Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan) within the framework of its "Neighbourhood Policy". Georgia is currently a candidate country for EU membership. The Minister of Foreign Affairs of Armenia has recently made a statement on Armenia's wish to join the European Union. The EU is guided by values that partner countries must adhere to. Currently, the EU is expanding its relations with all three states. Naturally, it is guided by its geopolitical interests. Therefore, the subject of this paper is relevant, both at the national and international levels.

The work was drawn on the methods of comparison, systemic analysis, historical dialectical and document study.

From the time when the European Union was established, the free development of nations and respect for fundamental human rights have been considered universally recognized principles. It is a union of free nations, where people are given full opportunity to develop, and the decisions are made by consensus. Of course, the EU applies its proven ideology of liberal democracy to expand its area i.e. the "free space". This is the approach that the European Union has been show-

ing within the framework of the "Neighbourhood Policy". The principle is simple, the countries striving to approximate to the European Union, must meet the standards set by it. We do not imply that geopolitics bears no importance to the EU, it undoubtedly does and often the EU has to manoeuvre around some international problem, but it adheres to principles when it comes to fundamental values.

The main areas of relations between the European Union and the South Caucasian states

Russia's invasion of Ukraine on 24th of February, 2022 significantly changed the global landscape and the trend of a new world order is being formed. The outcome of this war is unknown, but one thing is certain: it will undoubtedly shape a new world order¹. The EU's relations with different regions are of great importance in the process of shaping that world order. Among them, the South Caucasus is becoming a very important region in light of the economic sanctions imposed on Russia. Europe considerably reduced its energy dependence on Russia at the same time imposing severe sanctions (13 packages in total). Under these circumstances, the South Caucasian energy corridor acquires even greater importance for the EU. Till now, the relations between the EU and South Caucasian countries were developing dynamically, Georgia received the bitter experience of Russian aggression in the separatist regions (Abkhazia and the so-called South Ossetia), unequivocally chose a pro-Western orientation, and today it is a state that was granted a candidate status of the European Union.

Armenia had a pro-Russian orientation from the beginning. Although since the last Karabakh war, as it lost control over this region, while Azerbaijan restored its territorial integrity at the end of 2023, Armenia is currently in an uncertain situation. It has recently suspended its membership in the Collective Security

¹ Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one

part, and the Republic of Georgia, of the other part, Official Journal of the European Union. 1999. 4 August.

Treaty Organization (CSTO) and further distanced itself from Russia. Obviously, Armenia strives to develop in a Western way but faces great challenges along the way.

At the moment, Azerbaijan looks morally and physically confident, having won the Karabakh war, restored its territorial integrity, established good relations with its neighbours (except Armenia), and officially declared neutrality. In our opinion, Azerbaijan pursues a pragmatic foreign policy. Most importantly, Azerbaijan, as a country rich in energy resources, is of great importance to the EU. This is a general contemporary overview of the South Caucasus region, and how the events develop further will greatly depend on the pragmatic policy of the political leadership of these states, as well as on the international situation.

Considering the abovementioned, it would seem reasonable to focus on relation dynamics between the EU and the South Caucasian countries in terms of promoting democratic reforms in these states.

Support for democratic reforms in some states can be considered the EU's "soft power", but this is where its real power lies, as many countries themselves strive to develop towards the European Union, because democracy is not a panacea, but the curtain journey to development, i.e. a means to an end.

Georgia, Armenia and Azerbaijan committed to establishing democracy early on when an agreement to build relations with the European Union in 1996 was achieved. It was then that the South Caucasian states signed a similar agreement on partnership and cooperation in the field of democracy and human rights². The agreement emphasized the rule of law, respect for human rights, recognition of minorities, establishment of a multi-party system with independent and democratic elections³.

Since Georgia and Armenia joined the "Eastern Partnership" program, the emphasis was moved to specific issues of developing democracy related to reforms of state institutions. For instance, the fourth point of the Comprehensive and Enhanced Partnership Agreement (CEPA) between Armenia and the EU, discusses the strengthening of stability, principles of democratic institutions and the rule of law. All the mentioned should become one of the main areas of internal reforms in Armenia⁴. The agreement does not define the meaning of "democracy", nor any mechanism through which democratic institutions were to be developed.

As for Georgia, the preamble of the Association Agreement, describes in detail the requirements for cooperation, and other types of reforms to democratic development. This is not surprising, as Georgia chose the pro-Western aspirations from the beginning. Therefore, it is a leading country in the South Caucasus in terms of EU integration. The document emphasizes that the European Union is based on the values of democracy, respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms, which become the basis of political association and economic integration. The fourth article states that the parties intend to cooperate to increase the stability and effectiveness of democratic institutions and the rule of law. Special attention is paid to the areas of judicial and legal reforms, public administration and the fight against corruption⁵. The eighth article focuses on regional stability and peaceful resolution of conflicts.

Georgia's choice is clear and it has always been the historical choice of the Georgian people. Historically, Georgia has always had a pro-Western orientation whenever it was given the slightest opportunity to do so. In the given historical context, even the pro-Russian orientation of the Georgian kings implied pro-Western leaning, as with the fall of Constantinople in 1453 and the Ottoman Empire neighbouring Georgia, it had only option to establish relations with Russia to get closer to the West. The bitter experience of relations with Russia finally convinced Georgia of the need to join the European house.

The current global realities complicate and obscure the full realization of the choice of the Georgian people. There is another factor involved. This is the understanding of democracy in the modern world. The interpretation of democracy in general has always raised questions from ancient Greece to the present day.

The definition of democracy differs in various types of states. Scientific papers and publications distinguish between the liberal-democratic model of the United States and the social-liberal model of the European Union. The UK's exit from the European Union was facilitated by the division of the British democratic model and the European continental democracy⁶. The model of Russian sovereign democracy is also worth noting, which claims to be a unique Russian democracy, where outside interference is made impossible.

Sometimes, scholars of international political opinion refer to the South Caucasian countries as hybrid regimes, where the formal signs of democratic governance and informal governance practices are seen, which is characteristic of authoritarianism. For in-

² Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Armenia, of the other part, Official Journal of the European Union. 1999. 9 September.

³ Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Azerbaijan, of the other part, Official Journal of the European Union. 1999. 17 September.

⁴ Comprehensive and Enhanced Partnership Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy

Community and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Armenia, of the other part, European Commission. 2017.

⁵ Association Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and Georgia, of the other part // Official Journal of the European Union. 2014. 13 August.

⁶ Буторина О., Сужение Европейского союза и потенциал интеграции, Современная Европа. 2020. No 2.

stance, according to them "slowly maturing democracy"⁷ is typical for Georgia, "competitive authoritarianism"⁸ for Armenia, and "semi-authoritarianism"⁹ for Azerbaijan. Apparently, Georgia has a certain degree of advantage when it comes to democracy, however, despite the political transformations in all South Caucasian countries, the authoritarian tendencies still adhere, and at the same time, they approximate to the West in various areas, including legal framework. The problem is that just functioning political institutions and the electoral system do not imply the transition to democratic governance. Scholars underscore the effectiveness of the criteria of democratic reforms, as it is in the European Union.

The EU Neighbourhood Policy with the South Caucasian states

Within the frame of its "neighbourhood policy", the European Union pays great attention to human rights and freedoms, as well as to the interests of individual social groups. The EU shows special interest in protecting the interests of vulnerable groups, gender and sexual minorities, and national minorities. This sometimes contradicts the Caucasian mentality and traditions. In this regard, "Family Sanctity" Day established by the Patriarchate of Georgia on the 17th of May in confrontation with the LGBT community is noteworthy. The speech of transgender women in the Armenian Parliament in 2019 during the session on the judicial system also played a considerable role and was followed by harsh criticism by a number of parliamentarians¹⁰.

The attention to individual rights and liberties gave a new stimulus to the democratic reforms in South Caucasian countries. In fact, the reforms shared the main areas of "human security" in international cooperation stated in the Helsinki Final Act (1975). With the Final Act, the military-political, economic and "human" dimensions acquired the same importance¹¹. These issues in the South Caucasian countries are still a matter of controversy.

In September 2012, the European Commission adopted the Communication "The Roots of Democracy and Sustainable Development: Europe's engagement with Civil Society in External Relations"¹². As a result, a new "player", the civil society gained a foothold in the relations between the European Union and developed countries. The European Union relies on the civil society in many countries. As such, the "civil society" is poorly developed in the South Caucasian countries, and the civil activists lack authority. That's why, so far the development of the civil society here has staggered.

According to the European Commission, the CSOs share the common goal of social progress and the global fundamental values of peace, freedom, equal rights and human dignity. The European Commission has defined three specific areas of work with similar organizations in partner countries: to promote a conducive environment for CSOs, to promote meaningful participation of CSOs in domestic policies and international processes, to increase local CSOs' capacity, which in a way emphasized the greatest role of civil society of an independent development actor.

The EU strives to expand the "space of freedom" in almost all spheres of social, economic and political life. This tendency was reflected in its relations with the South Caucasian countries. In the early years of the "Neighbourhood Policy", the democratic reforms of the European Union were discussed in connection with the efforts to reduce poverty in different countries. Eradication of poverty in third-world countries and the protection of human rights were part of the main programmatic document for the EU adopted by the European Consensus on Development by the European Commission¹³.

Thus, the EU has contradictory relations with the South Caucasian countries. However, some things are common. Even though Georgia first signed an Association Agreement with the EU in 2014, and then, in 2023, became a candidate for EU membership¹⁴, while Armenia and Azerbaijan chose a different format for relations, the cooperation between the EU and the South Caucasian countries in terms of democratic reforms never implied the transformation of political regimes. In our opinion, this was due to geopolitical factors.

Azerbaijani and Armenian experience so far (at least until Azerbaijan's territorial integrity is restored) indicated that even if the countries do not make strong statements in support of democracy, or even partially fulfil their obligations under the agreement, cooperation with the EU can continue under mutually beneficial conditions¹⁵. This way Azerbaijan and Armenia were able to maintain the multi-vector nature of their foreign policy, without taking on the entire range of obligations.

Currently, the situation has changed. Armenia lost against Azerbaijan. Russia did not or could not help it. Accordingly, it is not excluded that Armenia will gradually start approximation to the European Union and fully share the values that are in the European Union. France is particularly active in this regard. Time will show all, especially the outcome of the war in Ukraine and the process of forming a new world order.

⁷ Delcour L., The EU's Unexpected "Ideal Neighbour"? The Perplexing Case of Armenia's Europeanisation, *Journal of European Integration*. 2015. 37(4):1.

⁸ Babayan N., A Global Trend EU-style: Democracy Promotion in "Fragile" and Conflict-Affected South Caucasus, *Global Policy*. 2016. Vol. 7, Is. 2.

⁹ Gulyev F., Post-Soviet Azerbaijan: Transition to Sultanistic Semiauthoritarianism? *Demokratizatsiya: The Journal of Post-soviet Democratization*. 2005.

¹⁰ Выступление трансгендера в парламенте Армении вызвало резонанс в соцсетях, Кавказский узел. 2019. 7 апреля.

¹¹ Paris R., Human Security: Paradigm Shift or Hot Air? *International Security*. 2001. Vol. 26, No 2.

¹² The roots of democracy and sustainable development: Europe's engagement with Civil Society in external Relations, European Commission. 2012.

¹³ The New European Consensus on Development "Our World, Our Dignity, Our future", European Commission. 2017.

¹⁴ Namchavadze B., Candidate status and new recommendations for the economy of Georgia, 2023

¹⁵ Kvakhadze A., Karabakh after the war: the main issues of politics and security, 2021

Conclusion

The EU acts as a partner integration union towards the South Caucasian countries, but at the same time, it represents a normative force in the relations with the states of the South Caucasus. This is its main principle because the European Union strives to expand the "space of freedom" within the framework of the "soft power" policy. This does not imply the EU imposing any special obligations on the partner country. The European Union is guided by its values, among which the protection of human rights and other freedoms, inviolability of private property, support of democratic principles, and implementation of both domestic and foreign policies based on consensus are of utmost importance. The EU holds its standards when it comes to economic policy. One cannot enter the EU market without complying with its standards. The EU implements all of it within its neighbourhood policy.

In terms of democracy, Georgia occupies a higher stance among the South Caucasian states compared to Armenia and Azerbaijan, however, due to geopolitical interests, the EU pays great attention to relations with Azerbaijan and Armenia. In this regard, partnership relations with Azerbaijan are particularly interesting, which are determined by Azerbaijan's significant reserves of natural resources. However, the recent developments in Armenia indicate there are chances that Armenia will soon express its aspiration to join the European Union.

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